

LINGUISTIC UNITS EXPRESSING NEGATION IN DIFFERENT SYSTEMIC LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

The article is a study in which the category of negation is analyzed on the material of languages of different systems. It should be noted that the category of negation can be expressed in different ways at different levels of language.

Introduction: The categories of negation and affirmation, according to Getmanova A.D., Bakharev A.I. and others, appeared among the first in the course of human thought development and were brought to absolute categories as defined by philosophers through the categories of existence / non-existence [1, 2].

Aristotle gave the negation the status of a logical category opposed to affirmation, using the concepts of lack, privation to express process of negation. He understands the negation as a logical form which shows that the thing in itself does not have something that it tends to have by its nature. The affirmation claims that an object has any characteristic, and the negation claims that an object lacks it. They exist in the relation of contradiction. Every affirmation opposes negation, every negation opposes affirmation [3].

Considering the negation as a lack when something does not have something, Aristotle calls one of the contradiction's

oppositions as the negation. One of oppositions acts as a lack of another: inequality is a lack of equality, dissimilarity is a lack of similarity, vice is a lack of virtue and so on. [3]. Thus, the negation is understood as opposition and the result of contradiction.

Main part: In formal logic, the negation is a logical process in the result of which, statement (proposition) A turns into statement (proposition) not-A, or statement not-A turns into statement A [2].

The negation is used to reject a false statement and oppose it a true one. However, affirmative or negative statements can be both true. Let's consider the examples given by Bakharev A.I.: The moon is a satellite of the Earth (affirmative statement), and It is not true that wood is metal (negative statement). These two statements are true. Likewise, affirmative and negative statements can be false. Consequently, the falsity and negation are the concepts of different sense [2].

In addition to the negation of a statement as a whole, classical logic considers the negation of a predicate, which is used to express that a subject doesn't have some characteristics.

The concepts of the negation in the philosophical and logical literature agree on one thing: affirmation and negation are treated as opposed in the statement quality. Bondarenko V.N. considers that an object in its quality distinctness can either exist or not exist, can either have some specific features or not have them. The lack of any object's specific feature is a real characteristic which has objective validity and has place in negative judgments. [4].

In linguistics, as there is no consensus concerning the category of negation. This problem was developed in several directions. In the psychological and pragmatic concepts of negation this category is defined either as a pure product of the human psyche, or just as intralingual function - expression of a speaker's view about someone else's thoughts.

The negation is also interpreted as a special form of modality and predication. Including the negation understood as a subjective assessment or unreality of anything into some certain modal meanings according to Bondarenko V.N. is connected with unjustified broad understanding of the category of modality. Predication does not depend on negative or affirmative form of a statement [4].

We also should pay attention to the concept of negation as an expression of the lack of objective connection.

Linguistic Dictionaries define the category of negation as an element of a sentence's meaning which indicates that the connection between the components of

a sentence according to a speaker is not real [5, 6, 7].

However according to Bakharev A.I. we can not flatly insist that by negating the connection between parts of a sentence does not really exist. Means of expressing negation not only persist but do not change the ways of syntactic context.

Defining the negation as a category when we can declare such unreal interrelation which actually have an absolute reality (chicken is not a bird) and such realities which no one would guess (iron is not stone) A.M. Peshkovskiy says not about the connection between parts of a sentence, but the concept connection, the reality/unreality of the connection between concepts and categories [8].

It is the lack of a certain kind of interrelation in the reality but not merely objective interrelations that should be seen as the negation referent. Negation is not just the lack of objective interrelations, but also the objects themselves and/or their characteristics, which include objective interrelations.

Logical negation and linguistic negation with their means of expression are comparable within their sense, but do not always absolutely correspond with each other. Many linguists (E.I. Shendels, O.V. Trunova et al.) note that the essence of the grammatical category of negation is logical negation. Shendels E.I. claims that the logical category of affirmation and negation is the main essence of the language category, but not entirely filled. The language category of affirmation and negation also performs other functions and has relative independence and its own volume of meanings not adequate with the logical category. Using of different means of negation in a sentence may have quite

different goals than the expression of a negative statement. In other words not every sentence with negation corresponds to a negative statement. It may correspond to a positive statement and serve as a mean of expression of not judgment, but prohibition, question and so on [9]. Trunova O.V. sees the difference between logical and grammatical negation in the universality of the first one and its ability to be expressed by different linguistic means [10].

Within the framework of cognitive linguistics the negation is considered as a concept, i.e. operational meaningful unit of thinking. The concept negation, as N.N.Boldyrev notes is the product of human consciousness as in the real world there is no lack of existence or occurrence and only human being makes it basing on his own experience and understanding of situation, basing on his own system of values, beliefs, assessments. At the heart of the language negation there is a classification concept which has a relative nature and obtains definite content only in relation with other concepts or conceptual framework [11].

In the statements of the people there are negations of different strength, ranging from a simple, barely noticeable disagreement with the views of another person, to categorical, irreversible

negation. Therefore in natural language there is quite a variety of means of negation expression, and therefore there are a number of theories based on different principles of analysis and classification criteria for the category of negation. Variety of approaches to studying this phenomenon can be reduced to two positions: the negation is considered either in terms of formal, or in terms of functional parameters. In the first case we have a binary opposition, one member of which is marked by the introduction of the negation index. Classification formed on the functional basis includes a formal classification as its component and distinguishes two negations: implicit and explicit.

There are a number of issues relating to the semantics of negation. The correct analysis of negation is a subject of ongoing debate in different fields of science, not least because it has wider implications than might at first be evident. The important matter of the discussion is a number of properties that are characteristic of various operations under the name negation, some of the reasons for and against considering some of them to be a correct account of negation and whether a variety of negations can coexist.

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